

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

The report presents global maps of weather risks, in particular extreme precipitation and heat, derived from the SR-ESM output.

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WP9

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Executive summary

The Hazard Hackathon took place in October 2024 in Wageningen under the lead of the Storms and Land theme. The focus of the hackathon was to develop code to extract information on extreme and high-impact events from the Cycle 4 production runs. In a second step, first maps of global and regional extreme events were produced. In this hackathon, the participants joined one of five topical challenges (efficient data handling and global maps of extremes, fireweather and near-surface humidity, renewable energy production, tropical cyclones in the West Pacific, hydrometeorological and temperature extremes) and the participants were thus mixed between themes. In preparation for the hackathon, two online training sessions for the participants provided technical information and the opportunity to ask for technical support.

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Objectives

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics.

The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with *yes*.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	yes
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | no |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | no |

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package as indicated below.

Objectives of WP9	Relevance in this deliverable?
Investigate whether resolving the storm-scale variability in weather systems and in the land surface, together with their consistent interactions with the larger scales, affects the climatology of blocking, the statistics of dry and warm spells, the mean surface radiation balance as well as near-term changes in aggregated temperature and precipitation statistics (O2)	no
Quantify the carbon stocks and fluxes over Europe at storm-resolving resolution and compare these estimates to ones from current ESMs (O2)	no
Use the production runs to reassess solar power on the global scale and to produce global maps of hazardous weather at unprecedented resolution (O3)	yes

1 Hackathon

1.1 Hackathon in numbers

The Hazard hackathon was hosted by the University of Wageningen (WUR) and took place in Wageningen from 14th to 18th October 2024. It was organized by the Land and Storms theme jointly by the PIs from WUR and the University of Bern. The decision to hold the hackathon in Wageningen rather than in Bern was based on the availability of rooms at the universities. A total of 83 participants joined the hackathon from 16 countries with 49 (59%) coming from nextGEMS and 34 coming from more than 11 different projects. 58% were early career scientists (Bachelor/ Master students, PhD candidates, Scientists up to 6 years after PhD) and 31 % were senior scientists. The remaining 11 % counting other backgrounds or occupations. The nextGEMS office gave five travel grants to attendees from low-income countries or students from other projects. More information on the hackathon is available here: <https://nextgems.pages.gwdg.de/hazard-hackathon/>

1.2 Hackathon program

The Hazard hackathon was organised slightly differently than the other hackathons. The focus was on the validation and exploitation of the production runs for the user-relevant indicators. The hackathon topics were not organised along the nextGEMS themes but according to five challenges that had been defined prior to the hackathon. Participants could then join one of the four pre-defined challenges or propose their own challenge. The four proposed challenges were:

- Efficient data handling and global maps of extreme weather: the goal of this challenge was to develop a processing chain that allowed researchers to create global maps of weather and climate extremes at zoom level 9 for all production runs.
- Fire weather: the goal of this challenge was to develop code to compute the fire weather index using nextGEMS models as input.
- Hydrological extremes: The goal of this challenge was to develop tools for the analysis of regional and global extremes related to the water cycle.
- Energy production: the goal of this challenge was to first validate indices relevant for energy production and then focus on extremes of these indices.
- Wild card challenge (participant defined): this challenge was intentionally left open to incorporate suggestions from the participants. The proposed additional topic was tropical cyclones.

The challenges were introduced during the pre-hackathon online training sessions. During the training sessions, the key programming tools necessary to access and process the data were introduced. The detailed hackathon program is available here: <https://nextgems.pages.gwdg.de/hazard-hackathon/>. The program included two invited talks

Figure 1: The difference in the number of tropical nights ($T_{min} > 20^{\circ}\text{C}$) per year between the IFS-FESOM historical and SSP3.7 runs.

and two side events, one introducing the Aqua Tools from Destination Earth and one on the needs of the energy sector. During the session on Friday morning, the results of the challenges were shared and discussed.

1.3 Efficient data handling and global maps of extremes challenge

The team focusing on global maps of extremes developed code to efficiently extract the ETCCDI indices (Zhang et al., 2011) from the production runs. The ETCCDI indices capture different aspects of moderate temperature and precipitation extremes. The task was accomplished, and two maps of example indicators are provided below in Figures 1 and 2. The first example shows an index (tropical nights) that is based on a fixed temperature threshold ($T_{min} > 20^{\circ}\text{C}$), Figure 1. A comparison between ICON and IFS-FESOM showed that ICON is systematically colder over land, and as a consequence, the number of tropical nights is lower than in the IFS-FESOM simulations. In a warmer climate the number of tropical nights increases in the subtropics and mid-latitudes. The number does not substantially change in the tropics, where the threshold is exceeded during most nights already in the present climate.

The global map of the 98th percentile of the wind speed derived from hourly instantaneous winds indicates the benefit of the high-resolution data. The effects of small islands and other topographic features on the wind field are clearly visible.

All indices are available as plots on Zenodo (Brunner, 2025b) and the underlying gridded data are available here (Brunner, 2025a). Brunner et al., 2025 describe the ETCCDI results in more detail.

Figure 2: The 98th percentile of the wind in the ICON production run.

1.4 Fire weather index and near surface humidity

The fire weather index and near surface humidity team developed code to calculate the FWI from nextGEMS model output and applied it to a sub-domain that includes California. The team managed to run the FWI calculations for the domain for all the production runs (ICON historical, IFS-FESOM historical, IFS-FESOM SSP3.7). The FWI values are consistent between IFS-FESOM and ICON. There is an increase in the FWI in IFS-FESOM between the historical and the SSP3.7 simulations (Figure 3).

Fire weather conditions are strongly modulated by the near-surface humidity. However, recent studies suggest that global climate models overestimate the increase of near-surface specific humidity and underestimate the decrease in relative humidity (Simpson et al., 2024). This is particularly pronounced for semi-arid regions such as California. First analyses of the near-surface specific humidity in the IFS-FESOM simulations show a decreasing trend in specific humidity over California but a global increase in specific humidity that exceeds the rates observed in ERA-5 (Figure 3).

At the hackathon, we decided to first look into changes of the individual components of the FWI before analysing the FWI in more detail. Publications on the near-surface humidity trends are currently in preparation.

1.5 Hydrological extremes

The group working on precipitation and temperatures extremes was the largest challenge group with a large variety of topics. These topics included examining mesocyclones over the Sahara

Figure 3: left panel: 99th percentile of the FWI in California in the IFS production runs; right panel global mean annual mean specific humidity in ERA-5 (blue line), in the IFS historical runs (orange line) and in the IFS production run (green line)

desert, a new river discharge model in IFS (Camaflood), jet stream patterns, European tropical cyclones, snow cover changes in the Spanish mountains, global water cycle changes, flooding in Poland, African Easterly Waves, multi-annual ocean and atmospheric variability, moisture tracking features, and the influence of various regridding methods. Here we only present three examples that focus on precipitation extremes. The first example (Figure 4) shows the temporal evolution of an extreme precipitation indicator. The Extreme precipitation multiplier ERM indicates if an extreme event exceeds the climatological mean extremest value per year (RX). The analysis indicates an increase in the extreme indicator globally according to SSP3.7 IFS-FESOM and thus a projected increase in extreme precipitation events. Next, Figure 5 shows an analysis of changes in extreme precipitation frequency in the IFS and ICON production runs aggregated globally and across all land and all ocean gridpoints. There is a much weaker increase in the precipitation extremes in ICON compared to IFS, especially at the tail-end values above the 99.9th quantile. Finally, Figure 6 shows the results of feeding the IFS model output into a discharge model (Camaflood) for the Danube catchment at Ingoldstadt. The implementation of the Camaflood model in the IFS-FESOM was still a work in progress however the participants were able to calculate the Danube river discharge along with baseflow index and runoff coefficient.

Global maps of extreme precipitation indicators are available on Zenodo (Brunner, 2025b).

1.6 Energy production

In this challenge, indicators of solar and wind energy production potential were extracted from the km-scale simulations (see Figure 7 for a global analysis of the wind capacity factor). A special focus was put on Spain as part of the renewable energy storyline project (Baulenas et al., 2025). The high spatial and temporal resolution of the nextGEMS simulations allows for the study of correlations between wind and solar potential (capacity factors). The results for Spain show very low spatial correlations between solar and wind capacity factors ($\rho = -0.010$). This indicates

Figure 4: IFS FESOM global extreme precipitation multiplier

Figure 5: Change in extreme precipitation in the IFS and ICON production runs

Figure 6: Results of coupling the IFS simulations with the Camaflood tool for the Danube catchment at Ingolstadt

that regions with high solar potential often do not coincide with those experiencing high wind potential at a given time. Such spatial decoupling implies a form of geographic complementarity: integrating solar and wind across different regions could help smooth out local fluctuations and reduce overall variability in renewable energy supply. Although no explicit temporal aggregation was performed in this analysis, the spatial diversity alone suggests potential benefits for grid balancing and energy system resilience.

1.7 Tropical cyclones challenge

The team in the tropical cyclone challenge applied the tempest extremes cyclone tracking routine to the historical IFS-FESOM (30 years) and ICON (Cycle 3, 5 years) data and to the SSP3.7 IFS-FESOM (30 years) and ICON (30 years) data sets. The tracking algorithm tracked low-pressure systems in the tropical West Pacific and the Indian Ocean and compared the present data results with the IBTrACS observational data set (see Figure 9 for example tracks detected in the ICON SSP3.7 simulations. Overall, both models capture the spatial track patterns of tropical cyclones in the West Pacific as well as the seasonality. Storm-centred analyses reveal an intensification of the tropical cyclones in the warmer climate simulations and associated increased extreme wind speed and rainfalls in the warmer simulations (Figure 9, right panel).

Wind energy capacity factor: 2020-2029 mean

Figure 7: left panel: wind capacity factor in the ICON production run; middle panel: wind capacity factor in the IFS production run; right panel: difference of the wind capacity factor IFS - ICON

Solar and wind have different spatial patterns in Spain

Figure 8: left panel: wind energy capacity factor in 2024 in the IFS historical run; right panel: solar energy capacity factor in 2024 in the IFS historical run

Figure 9: Left panel: tropical cyclone tracks in the Indian Ocean and the West Pacific identified with the Tempest tracking tool (Ullrich et al., 2021) in the ICON SSP3.7 simulations. Right panel: tropical cyclone counts per year in the historical IFS simulation and historical ICON (Cycle 3, 5-years), IFS the SSP3.7 simulations and the ICON SSP3.7 simulation compared to observations (IBTrACS)

2 Conclusion

The hackathon has been successful, global indicators of weather extremes have been extracted from the 30-year simulations at the highest resolution. The data are now publicly available. All figures shared in this report were produced at the hackathon and are, hence, in a preliminary state and are not refined figures for scientific publications. Follow-up publications by the hackathon will provide more refined and in-depth analyses and data validations will become available in the coming months.

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